

P2GREEN: ΠΡΟΩΘΗΣΗ ΤΩΝ ΚΥΚΛΙΚΩΝ ΡΟΩΝ ΘΡΕΠΤΙΚΩΝ ΣΥΣΤΑΤΙΚΩΝ ΜΕΣΩ ΤΗΣ ΑΝΑΠΤΥΞΗΣ ΤΩΝ ΒΙΟΛΙΠΑΣΜΑΤΩΝ

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ΠΕΡΙΛΗΨΗ

Το P2Green, ένα τετραετές έργο Horizon Europe που επικεντρώνεται στο κλείσιμο της αλυσίδας μεταξύ αγροκτήματος και πιρουνιού για κυκλικές ροές θρεπτικών ουσιών. Θα δοκιμάσει και θα προσαρμόσει τη χρήση των ανθρώπινων υγειονομικών αποβλήτων για την παραγωγή ασφαλών, βιολογικών λιπασμάτων για τη γεωργία, τα οποία θα αντικαταστήσουν τα λιπάσματα ορυκτής προέλευσης. Δοκιμάζει τρεις καινοτόμες τεχνολογίες ανακύκλωσης θρεπτικών ουσιών σε τρεις πιλοτικές περιοχές στη Γερμανία, την Ισπανία και τη Σουηδία. Οι πιλοτικές περιοχές έχουν επιλεγεί προσεκτικά, καθώς καταδεικνύουν τη σύνδεση μεταξύ των αστικών (πιρουνί) και των αγροτικών (αγρόκτημα) κοινοτήτων. Ταυτόχρονα, διερευνάται η δυνατότητα αναπαραγωγής και κλιμάκωσης αυτών των τεχνολογιών σε άλλες χώρες της ΕΕ όπως η Ιταλία, η Ελλάδα, η Ουγγαρία και η Γαλλία. Σκοπός είναι να προσαρμοστεί κάθε πιλοτική τεχνολογία σε μια συγκεκριμένη γεωγραφική περιοχή με βάση τα χαρακτηριστικά και τις ανάγκες της.

Στην Ελλάδα θα πραγματοποιηθούν τρεις μελέτες σκοπιμότητας, μια για κάθε πιλοτική τεχνολογία του P2Green, για να εξακριβωθεί η δυνατότητα εφαρμογής σε εθνικό επίπεδο. Η πρώτη λύση διαχωρίζει τα πολύτιμα ούρα στην πηγή χρησιμοποιώντας μια τουαλέτα εκτροπής ούρων ή ουρητήριο και το τελικό προϊόν λίπανσης είναι σε μορφή pellet. Στην Ελλάδα έχει προσδιοριστεί ως σημείο εφαρμογής μια εταιρεία μίσθωσης φορητών τουαλετών, καθώς απαιτείται μόνο η αντικατάσταση των τουαλετών χωρίς να διαφοροποιείται ιδιαίτερα η καθημερινή λειτουργία της επιχείρησης. Η δεύτερη λύση αξιοποιεί μια τουαλέτα εκτροπής ούρων και το τελικό προϊόν λίπανσης είναι σε υγρή μορφή. Η εγκατάσταση πραγματοποιείται σε κτηριακά συγκροτήματα και απαιτεί την ύπαρξη ενός δεύτερου δικτύου αποχέτευσης που θα συλλέγει μόνο τα ούρα και θα τα επεξεργάζεται επί τόπου σε κάποιο βοηθητικό χώρο του κτηρίου. Συνεπώς η εφαρμογή της κρίνεται οικονομοτεχνικά συμφέρουσα σε κτήρια υπό κατασκευή ή ριζική ανακαίνιση όπως το κτήριο Ρουσόπουλου του Γεωπονικού Πανεπιστημίου Αθηνών. Τέλος, η τρίτη λύση αξιοποιεί τη δευτεροβάθμια εκροή επεξεργασίας μιας εγκατάστασης επεξεργασίας αστικών αποβλήτων για την παραγωγή ενός πλούσιου σε θρεπτικά συστατικά νερού για άρδευση. Ο βιολογικός καθαρισμός της Καρδίτσας αποτελεί μια χαρακτηριστική περίπτωση λόγω της εγγύτητάς του σε αγροτικές εκμεταλλεύσεις.

Παράλληλα, η εφαρμογή των εν λόγω τεχνολογιών εξετάζεται υπό το πρίσμα του υφιστάμενου νομοθετικού πλαισίου της Ευρωπαϊκής Ένωσης και της Ελλάδας, το οποίο ρυθμίζει τη διαχείριση των συγκεκριμένων υλικών σε διάφορα επίπεδα, από την πρώτη ύλη έως το τελικό προϊόν. Η Ευρωπαϊκή Ένωση προωθεί νομοθετικά τη μετάβαση προς την κυκλική οικονομία, ενισχύοντας την ανακύκλωση και την επαναχρησιμοποίηση πόρων, ωστόσο εξακολουθούν να υπάρχουν κενά και προκλήσεις στην πλήρη εφαρμογή των αρχών κυκλικότητας σε επιμέρους ρεύματα αποβλήτων.

Λέξεις κλειδιά: κυκλικές ροές θρεπτικών ουσιών, από το αγρόκτημα στο τραπέζι, αέρια και υδάτινη ρύπανση, λιπάσματα, διαχείριση λυμάτων

P2GREEN: PROMOTING NUTRIENT RECYCLING THROUGH THE DEVELOPMENT OF BIOFERTILIZERS

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ABSTRACT

P2Green, a four-year Horizon Europe project focusing on closing the chain between farm and fork for cyclical nutrient flows. It will test and adapt the use of human sanitary waste to produce safe, bio-based fertilizers for agriculture, which will replace fertilizers of mineral origin. It is testing three innovative nutrient recycling technologies in three pilot sites in Germany, Spain and Sweden. The pilot sites have been carefully selected as they demonstrate the link between urban (fork) and rural (farm) communities. At the same time, the possibility of replicating and scaling up these technologies in other EU countries such as Italy, Greece, Hungary and France is being explored. The aim is to adapt each pilot technology to a specific geographical area based on its characteristics and needs.

In Greece, three feasibility studies will be carried out, one for each P2Green pilot technology, to verify the feasibility of implementation at national level. The first solution separates valuable urine at source using a urine diversion toilet or urinal and the final fertilization product is in pellet form. In Greece, a company renting portable toilets has been identified as a point of application, as only the replacement of the toilets is required without any significant deviation to the daily operation of the business. The second solution utilizes a urine diversion toilet, and the final fertilization product is in liquid form. It is installed in building complexes and requires the existence of a second

sewerage system that collects only the urine and treats it on site in an ancillary area of the building. It is therefore considered to be economically advantageous in buildings under construction or undergoing radical renovation, such as the Rousopoulos building of the Agricultural University of Athens. Finally, the third solution utilises the secondary treatment effluent of a municipal waste treatment plant to produce a nutrient-rich water for irrigation. The biological treatment of Karditsa is a typical case due to its proximity to agricultural holdings.

At the same time, the application of these technologies is examined in the light of the existing legislative framework of the European Union and Greece, which regulates the management of these materials at various levels, from raw material to final product. The European Union is legislatively promoting the transition towards a circular economy, enhancing recycling and reuse of resources, but there are still gaps and challenges in the full implementation of circularity principles in individual waste streams.

Keywords: circular nutrient flows, farm to fork, air and water pollution control, fertilizer, wastewater management

1. Introduction

Worldwide food demand is on the rise, driven primarily by population growth and increasing per capita consumption, particularly in developing nations. Projections indicate a significant increase in global food production will be needed to meet this demand by 2050 (OECD/FAO, 2025). To cope with the increased food demand, farmers are using more and more mineral fertilizers, such as nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P), to combat soil degradation in over-exploited agricultural land. Due to the excessive use of fertilizers, nutrient losses cause a major threat to the environment, especially on aquatic ecosystems. They cause surface and groundwater pollution and phenomena such as eutrophication (Mustafa et al., 2023). Additionally, mineral-based fertilizers are heavily dependent on fossil fuels, both during the production and application phase, contributing significantly to the release of CO_{2e} emissions in the atmosphere and therefore intensifying climate change (Walling et al., 2020). Mineral fertilizers are not only a potential threat to the environment but also a liability for the European Union since they are typically being produced outside the EU. Due to limited supplies of fossil fuels and high price-volatility of energy prices, imported fertilizers are a direct threat to the Union's food security (Vermeulen et al., 2012).

Overfertilization leads also to high nutrient concentration, through food consumption, in human excreta and ultimately to water bodies after undergoing treatment in wastewater treatment plants. Typically, the majority of nitrogen is being removed from the wastewater stream, through denitrification, but is being released into the atmosphere in the form of molecular nitrogen. The removal of phosphorus takes place only in some cases (Papp et al., 2023).

2. P2GREEN: Fostering a paradigm shift

Agriculturally grown food is produced with the addition of energy-intensive fertilizers. Then the food is transported to large city centers and is being consumed. Wastewater treatment plants treat human excreta by removing the majority of the nutrients where disposing the rest in water bodies causing major environmental problems. It would make more sense to turn this linear chain of events into a cycle that reduces the production of mineral fertilizers, minimize the environmental impact and increase food security. P2Green's goal is to close the nutrient loop between the cities (fork) and the rural areas where food is being produced (farm) as shown in figure 1.

Figure 1: Developing a nutrient cycle between urban (fork) and rural (farm) areas.

To achieve this paradigm shift, P2GreenN will bring together industry, farmers, researchers, policy makers, public entities and local governments to develop various pathways on how nutrients can be recovered and reused. It will follow a multi-sectoral approach, ranging from innovative technologies and circular business models to value chain and governance framework development. The innovative technological approaches will be tested and validated to efficiently recover nutrients at the source through the implementation of three living labs in Sweden, Germany and Spain. Additionally, it will maximize its impact by implementing feasibility studies in France, Greece, Hungary and Italy.

2.1. Methodology in the pilot regions

P2GreenN's technological concept will be demonstrated and validated in the three P2GreenN pilot regions and will be later scaled up to four follower regions. Each approach is suited to the specificities of each region taking into account the waste streams, crop production, available resources as well as the policy framework.

In the Swedish pilot region, urine is typically being collected from portable toilets installed in festivals in the island of Gotland. Instead of being disposed to the city's wastewater treatment plant, urine is stabilized by adding a chemical stabilizer and then

dried to increase its concentration and minimize its volume. Once dry it is then pelletized and ready to be applied on the fields using conventional farming equipment as shown in figure 2. The circular bio-fertilizer is mostly used to fertigate barley for beer production so that the cycle can repeat itself.

Solution Process

Sanitation360

Figure 2: The Swedish pilot region solution.

The German pilot region follows the same principle by collecting urine at the source. It utilizes portable toilets to collect the urine, but it also separates the urine by installing urine-diverting toilets and separation networks in buildings. Once collected, urine goes through a bioreactor for nitrification and then an activated carbon filter for pharmaceuticals elimination. Then water evaporates to increase concentration. The final product is liquid fertilizer. Additionally, the German pilot collects faeces, from the portable toilets, and produces a nutrient-rich compost as shown in figure 3.

Figure 3: The German pilot region solution.

The Spanish pilot region follows a different approach by utilizing the outflow of the secondary treatment of the municipal wastewater treatment plant. After treatment through a membrane bioreactor (MBR), the recycled water is rich in nutrients and suitable for irrigation/fertigation. A smart fertigation is being developed to measure the crops' intake of nutrients, and conventional fertilizer is added if necessary.

Figure 4: The Spanish pilot region solution.

3. Legislative framework for scaling P2Green solutions

The legislative framework plays a critical role in determining whether P2Green's pilot solutions can be scaled-up. Even effective solutions may face legal restrictions, making early analysis essential. This is especially relevant when scaling across regions or countries with differing legal systems. A legal and regulatory expert team within P2Green conducted a scoping review of the regulatory landscape affecting P2Green solutions. Key frameworks reviewed relate to waste, fertilizing products, reclaimed water, and organic farming. Their final report will include tailored recommendations for implementing circular solutions in the pilot and follower regions.

3.1 Waste and Urban Wastewater

At the EU level, the Waste Framework Directive (WFD) and the Urban Waste Water Treatment Directive (UWWTD) are key. However, they do not clearly define separately collected human urine as wastewater. As EU Directives, these require national transposition, leaving Member States to interpret and implement provisions independently. Treated urine's intended use as fertilizer complicates classification;

whether it remains waste or reaches “end-of-waste” status is still unclear and depends on national interpretation, given the absence of EU-wide end-of-waste criteria.

In Greece, Law No. 4042/2012 and Ministerial Decision 5673/400/1997 transpose the WFD and UWWTD, respectively. However, neither clarifies how to categorize source-separated excreta. Discussions with authorities revealed that although urine does not enter the sewage system, it might still be classified as domestic wastewater. Alternatively, since it is not discharged into water bodies, the UWWTD may ultimately not apply and therefore would be categorized as waste under the WFD, necessitating classification in the European Waste Catalogue. Legal uncertainty over the classification impacts permitting and transport, underscoring the need for EU and national clarification.

3.2 Fertilizing products

Fertilizing products, such as fertilizers, biostimulants, and soil improvers, can be placed on the EU market via:

- National authorization in a Member State (limited to that Member State)
- EU Fertilizing Products Regulation (FPR) (Regulation EU 2019/1009), allowing CE-marked products to be sold EU-wide.

To qualify as an EU fertilizing product under the Regulation, a product must a) comply with a Product Function Category (PFC) based on its intended use and quality characteristics, b) contain ingredients compliant with a Component Material Category (CMC), c) undergo and pass a suitable conformity assessment and d) carry the appropriate labelling.

While the Regulation allows certain waste streams as inputs under categories like CMC15, source-separated urine is not yet included. However, a technical study by NMI B.V., commissioned by the European Commission, is currently evaluating the inclusion of (treated) urine as an allowed input material in the Regulation.

In Greece, the core regulatory framework consists of Law No. 1565/85, laying general rules for fertilizers, and the recently published Ministerial Decision 50424/2025, which define the types of fertilizers that may be placed on the market without prior authorization as well as types of non-fertilizing products. This provision specifies minimum nutrient content thresholds, permitted raw materials, and acceptable production methods.

The urine-derived fertilizer developed in the German pilot region, does not meet the minimum nutrient quantities to qualify as fertilizer under these rules. In contrast, Sweden’s pelletized fertilizer meets the criteria for classification as a compound solid

fertilizer. Moreover, national regulations currently allow only “solid products or solutions from chemical synthesis or physical mixing.” The production processes used by P2Green may not conform to this requirement, since the fertilizers are produced through the treatment of urine to recover nutrients and not by chemical synthesis or by mixing various raw materials together. So, potentially the introduction of a new fertilizer type that also accounts for the nutrient content found in the liquid urine-derived fertilizer is needed. This can be achieved by submitting a technical dossier for evaluation in accordance with Ministerial Decision 291180/11034/2002.

3.3 Reclaimed water for irrigation

The EU Water Reuse Regulation (EU 2020/741) promotes reclaimed water for agricultural irrigation. It mandates additional treatment of treated wastewater under the UWWTD to meet defined water quality classes (based on crop risk levels), covering microbiological and chemical parameters, and requires Risk Management Plans addressing 11 key risk elements. Member States can opt out or limit reuse based on local conditions.

In Greece, Joint Ministerial Decision 145/116/2011 governs reuse of treated wastewater and permits its use for various purposes, including agricultural irrigation. It distinguishes restricted (e.g., animal feed, processed crops) and unrestricted (e.g., raw-consumed crops) irrigation based on crop exposure, with detailed treatment and safety requirements. Permits are needed for water reuse which are granted to users or operators and may fall under broader environmental permitting regimes, depending on the case.

A new Ministerial Decision is being drafted to harmonize Greece’s legal framework on water reuse with EU requirements.

4. Feasibility Studies in Greece – Data and initial results

Greece is one of the four follower regions of the project. All three pilot cases will be tested in Greece to showcase their strengths, weaknesses and adaptability in southern Europe.

4.1 Swedish pilot region feasibility in Greece

In Greece we have identified a portable toilet renting company to test the feasibility of the Swedish pilot region. The portable toilet market in Greece is dominated by mainly two companies based in Athens which serve other Greek major cities as well. Many

smaller companies do exist and operate at the local level. The typical portable toilet holds around 260 liters of liquid and requires 25 ml of treatment chemical to avoid odor issues.

Portable toilets are typically used at events (e.g. music festivals) and construction sites. For events, one toilet is required for every 70-80 attendees. On the other hand, one toilet is required for every 10 construction site workers with cleaning/emptying on a weekly basis. On average, each toilet generates 16 liters of wastewater per day, but this figure varies significantly depending on the occasion. For events, each toilet generates around 27 liters of wastewater daily.

Utilizing a portable urine diverting toilet or portable urinal will slightly increase the complexity of transportation and handling logistics. Additionally, the cleaning staff should be trained in how to handle the valuable urine. The vast majority of the operation's costs are associated with cleaning and transportation costs. While the cost of disposing the wastewater in the conventional treatment plant is currently minimal at 8 euros for 10 m³ of wastewater. Therefore, under the current **legislative** framework and the fact that wastewater treatment plants do not measure the quality of incoming pollutants but just the quantity, there is no financial benefit to allow room for such initiatives. Lastly, such enterprises are typically located in peri-urban areas and thus the transportation cost of treated urine to the field needs to be accounted for.

4.2 German pilot region feasibility in Greece

The majority of Greek population resides in large city centers with almost half living in Athens metropolitan area. Multistory buildings in Greece are typically built between 1960-1970 with minimal backup spaces that treatment equipment could potentially be installed. Therefore, installing a secondary piping network to collect urine proves to be a financial and technical challenge that can potentially be applied only in new construction or in buildings undergoing major renovations. Additionally, to benefit from the economies of scale such applications prove to be ideal for large public buildings such as schools, hospitals etc.

For the above reasons, the Roussopoulos building of the Athens Agricultural University, that recently went through major renovations, was chosen as the best candidate for the conduction of the feasibility study. The first step was to calculate the people using the building (students, academic and technical staff) based on the academic curriculum and in-person interviews. The average urine production per adult and day is 1.3 liters (Martin et al., 2020), resulting in a total of around 51 liters per day for the building based on student attendance data. Given the fact that the German urine treatment system is designed for an input of around 500 liters per day, initial results show that the system is better suited for larger building complexes or urine collected elsewhere could potentially compensate to make it more feasible.

4.3 Spanish pilot region feasibility in Greece

For the Spanish pilot technology, the city of Karditsa was identified as a feasibility case. First, the wastewater treatment plant is ideally located at the edge of the city and close to agricultural fields that require irrigation. Second, the facility outflow exceeds certain discharge quality criteria, such as total nitrogen. Therefore, the municipal utility will need to address this issue in the near future, potentially by utilizing a similar technology to the Spanish pilot. Additionally, the region faces water scarcity that threatens to impact agricultural production.

The most prominent method to tackle such problems seems to be water recycling. Combining water with nutrient recycling will not only provide solutions to two major problems but also minimize the facility's treatment costs. We have identified the facility's inflow and outflow characteristics as well as the needs of the crops (irrigation, fertigation, prices, yields, etc.). To better illustrate the potential pathways, four scenarios will be developed with each one simulating irrigation water complying with class A (food crops consumed raw) and class D (energy crops).

- Scenario 0: Business as usual
- Scenario 1: WWTP compliant with limits, apply water recycling
- Scenario 2: WWTP not compliant with limits, apply water recycling
- Scenario 3: WWTP not compliant with limits, apply nature-based solution and water recycling

5. Conclusions

Water scarcity in the European Union has been identified as one of the main challenges for the foreseeable future. Together with the food crisis and price uncertainty, they pose a great threat to the livelihoods of millions in the EU. P2Green offers three solutions to tackle these emerging challenges in a local context. Each pilot technology can be applied at various points along the wastewater stream based on the needs and specificities of each application.

Each technology has its strengths and weaknesses. All of them are applicable in the Greek ecosystem but the Spanish technology, based on our research and initial data, stands out. It has the biggest impact in terms of water recycling and can be applied on a large scale to existing infrastructure. Collecting urine from portable toilets and urinals can be applied easily but has limited impact due to the low volume of wastewater processed. On the other hand, urine diverting toilets separate urine efficiently on the source but pose a significant technical difficulty to install in existing buildings. Additionally, the legislation governing wastewater reuse is more clearly defined and comprehensive, especially at the EU level, compared to the regulatory framework for separated urine and its by-products, which remains relatively underdeveloped and fragmented. However, the Greek framework for water reuse in agriculture must soon be updated to align with Regulation (EU) 2020/741.

However, steps forward are required in terms of operational efficiency and local engagement. Currently, wastewater treatment plants do not measure the quality of incoming wastewater but rather the quantity. Therefore, key actors are not motivated to reduce the pollutant load of their waste stream. Additionally, municipalities must create a symbiotic environment between the utilities, farmers, local associations and business owners to make the most out of a “wasted” resource.

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